

Speaking Skill in English of Primary Students

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Abstract

The main objective of the study was to know the interests of private school students towards English as well as to ascertain the status of teaching learning in English at private primary school by survey method. With the help of tools like self prepared questionnaire, interview and classroom observation facts were gathered from 35 students and five teachers. Quantitative and qualitative methods of analysis were adopted to find out result. 80% of students like English as a subject but 60% of students were afraid of speaking because of fear of being wrong, shyness and source of humor. Opportunity to speaking second language was not up to the standard.

Keywords: Speaking Skill, Primary School.

Introduction

Our country is a multilingual nation where 87 languages are employed in print media and 71 languages re used in audio media. But only 47 languages are worked as the medium of instruction in school, English is one of the languages which acquired the status of associate official language at the national level. More than a century, it is utilized yet a very few can speak it. The Kunzru Committee (1959) recommended English as second language. The Central Advisory Board for Education (CABE) suggested the three language formula. This proposal was accepted by the conference of chief ministers in 1961. It becomes one of the three languages to be taught at upper primary level. Later on most of the States introduced it at the primary level. National Curriculum Framework, 2005 also states, "English may be one of the languages for learning activities that create the child's awareness of the world" In order to bring mastery over that language, one has to acquire four skills i.e listening, speaking, reading and writing. NCERT (2009-10) conducted a survey on teaching of English in Government primary school all over India. The survey showed teachers' less effort to develop listening and speaking skill. In most of the States teachers thought that by developing reading and writing skills of the students' will automatically evolve listening and speaking skills. However to learn foreign language one has to first of all bring mastery over the listening and speaking skill. Speaking is a productive skill comes after receptive skill. Speaking skill is a complex process that comprises of pronunciation of words, morphology and lexis (words and their parts), grammar and syntax (structure), semantics, discourse (conversation and utterance), pragmatics (usages and its rule), fluency (ease of speech, coherence, confidence and speech) besides topicality (themes and ideas).

Review of related literature

Scrivener, 2005 expresses four conditions like exposure, opportunities to use the language, motivation and instruction are essential for oral language learning. Willis, 1997 point out learners need possibilities to express what they think or feel and to experiment in a supportive atmosphere using language they have heard or seen without feeling threatened. Ahmed M.M.Nakhalah (2016) stated in his research study that difficulties faced by the students were fear of mistake, shyness, anxiety and lack of confidence. Zhengdong Gan (2012) set up factors that impeded spoken communication in English i.e insufficient opportunities to speak English in classroom and tutorials, lack of focus on language

upswing in the curriculum and input poor environment. Doan Linh Chi (2011) pointed out practice was an important part of language learning. Students should be encouraged to practice as much as possible. Some students do not know how to practice perfectly if not they feel disappointed not getting any fruit in their studies. Rababah (2005) pointed out a few factors like teaching strategies, curriculum cause difficulties in speaking English language. Qutbi Alam, Ayesha Bashir Uddin (2013)'s research on the improvement of oral Communication Skills had found that opportunity for practice oral language, providing conducive learning environment and using new strategies were helpful in oral communication of English language. Code switching, peer and self error correction, short pauses and speech fillers are inevitable for developing speaking skills of foreign language. NCERT (2012) expressed that the State text books gave less attention on the listening and speaking skills. Government school students got less opportunity for narration and exchange of ideas in English. N. Priyadarshani and Sharma, S.(2020) in their study found 78% students like English 90% of the students were hardly speak due to shyness, sense of humour and fear of wrong pronunciation.

Objectives of the study

1. To find out the interest of primary school students towards English language.
2. To know the status of teaching learning process in English at private primary school.

Methodology

Survey method was used for this study.

Sample : Random sampling technique was adopted for selecting sample. Cuttack district of Odisha was opted for the study. Thirty five students studying in class 5th, 6th and 7th and five English teachers teaching from the following English medium private schools were taken as sample of the study:

- 1) Maculary International School, Trisulia, Cuttack.
- 2) Modern Public School, Bidanasi, Cuttack

Tools: Following tools were wielded for data collection i.e

- i) Self prepared questionnaire based on students interest towards English
- ii) Interview
- iii) Classroom observation

Data Collection: The investigator personally visited the schools for data collection. Questionnaires were distributed among the students to measure the interest towards English language. Discussions with teachers on teaching learning process were accomplished. Class room observation and interview on various curricular and co-curricular activities of both teachers and students were documented.

Statistics: For analysis of data both quantitative and qualitative methods were adopted. Here percentage (%) was calculated.

Findings and Discussion

After an analytical study and interview with the student students take this as difficult. Teachers are very much careful towards their teaching style and their s of both the schools it is found that, English is the most liking subject for 80% of the students. A few teaching methodology. The students don't have any complaint regarding their teachers for their teaching. Teachers here do their best to make the topic very clear to the learners. Mainly the students get a strong support from their parents for their study. Their parents mostly interact with them in English. The atmosphere of their home forces them to increase their learning skills of English language. And those students who said English is a difficult subject, shows lack of interest towards the language. 60% of the students afraid of speaking due to fear of wrong pronunciation, shyness and sense of humour so, a skill of motivation may be required for them to create a better interest and confidence towards English. Unfortunately, most of the school teachers are not fluent in English and they are unable to teach the English language orally. They teach English in the form of written language to students and this is not a hundred percent learning. English teaching is best done when the teachers teach the language orally. Since the students are not interested to learn English, so they get tired of repeating and practicing the language. If the language is taught by the use of audio and video, then the students will learn it within a short period of time. Teachers can

also use some specific methods which are from the experiences of teachers in order to motivate the students in learning English.

Some students mentioned that learning English is the function of the teacher's characteristics, so that if students love their teachers and use his motivation and creativity, they will be more interested in English. So in some schools, the lack of creative teachers and the lack of access to equipment and limited content of incomplete course books minimize the student's performance.

Education is a pretty broad concept that surpasses the four walls of a classroom. The core aim of the education is to foster all round development essentially means intellectual, physical, moral, and social development. All round development can be achieved only through involvement on co-curricular activities. That is the only thing which English medium students do. A Chinese proverb very aptly states, "Teach me, and I will forget. Show me, and I will might remember. Involve me, and I will never forget". To a very great extent, the theoretical knowledge is enhanced when a co-curricular activity related to the content taught. Co-curricular activities are vital because even though they are not a part of the core curriculum, they play a very crucial role in giving the young boys and girls the ability to mould their lives to become well rounded people.

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